

STRUCTURAL ROBUSTNESS ANALYSIS OF ANISOGRID LATTICE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to compare the structural robustness of anisogrid composite lattice structures with orthogrid composite structures when subjected to axial compression. Due to multiple redundant load paths the anisogrid structure should have a higher structural robustness in comparison to orthogrid structures.

Within the framework of the EU-Project PoLaRBEAR (Production and Analysis Evolution for Lattice Related Barrel Elements under Operations with Advanced Reliability) anisogrid composite lattice structures are investigated in terms of a suitable primary fuselage alternative for aircrafts. The structural energy, the area under the load-shortening curve between several characteristic points such as the ultimate and collapse load, is evaluated using nonlinear FEM simulations in order to assess the structural robustness of anisogrid composite structures.

The results indicate an overall higher structural robustness of the anisogrid structures in comparison to the orthogrid structures for different load cases. In addition anisogrid structures seem to be more insensitive to the simulated impact damages than orthogrid structures.

As result, an answer is given if the anisogrid structure concept is a suitable design concept for fuselage structures in commercial aircrafts in terms of structural robustness.

1 INTRODUCTION

Anisogrid (Anisotropic Grid) composite lattice structures are currently used in the Russian heavy space launcher Proton-M as payload adapter as well as upper and lower interstages of the second stage [1]. An advantage of those structures in comparison to conventional used aluminum aerospace structures is a considerably lower weight resulting in an increase of the possible payload as well as a completely integral and therefore cost efficient manufacturing process. The question whether anisogrid composite lattice structures are also suitable as structural elements in aircraft application, is currently investigated in the EU-project PoLaRBEAR (Production and Analysis Evolution for Lattice Related Barrel Elements under Operations with Advanced Reliability). A possible area of application for the composite lattice structures in a commercial aircraft are fuselage, fin or wing. Another advantage of anisogrid composite lattice structures is a possible higher structural robustness. In order to investigate the structural robustness of an anisogrid or orthogrid panel a non-linear post-buckling analysis has to be performed. The commercial FEM software ABAQUS is used within this paper to calculate the structural energy (strain energy), the area under the load-shortening curve between several characteristic points such as the ultimate and collapse load is evaluated in order to assess the structural robustness of anisogrid structures.

2 INVESTIGATED SPECIMEN

An anisogrid lattice structure, originally described by Vasiliev et al. [2], consists of helical aligned (diagonal) and transverse monolithic stiffeners (blade stiffeners). In this investigation an anisogrid prepreg concept is analyzed which has in addition a load bearing skin. (Figure 1 - left).

Figure 1: Plane anisogrid structure (left) – plane orthogrid structure (right)

For the purpose of comparison a panel with axial aligned stiffeners as well as transverse stiffeners (orthogrid) and load bearing skin is also investigated. The flat panels are defined by the geometric parameters in Table 1. The manufacturing concept, materials etc. are equal to those of the anisogrid panel.

Geometry Parameter	Abbreviation	Dimension
Skin Thickness	t_s	[mm]
Transverse Stiffener Thickness	t_c	[mm]
Helix/Axial Stiffener Thickness	$t_{h/a}$	[mm]
Transverse Stiffener Distance	d_c	[mm]
Helix Angle	φ	[$^\circ$]
Transverse Stiffener Height	h_c	[mm]
Helix/Axial Stiffener Height	$h_{h/a}$	[mm]
Panel Length	a	[mm]
Panel Width	b	[mm]

Table 1: Geometry parameter of the panels

Using this approach it is possible to primarily investigate the influence of the two different stiffener arrangements on the structural behavior under axial compression, especially the post-buckling behavior and structural robustness. The flat panels are analytical pre-designed, no global panel buckling, local stiffener buckling and material failure until ultimate load is allowed. In order to investigate the post-buckling behavior with respect to current primary airframe standards skin buckling is allowed at limit load. A wide range of sized panels has been investigated, see Table 2.

Loads (Ultimate load - UL)	Orthogrid	Anisogrid
200 N/mm		A200
250 N/mm	O250	A250
400 N/mm		A400
500 N/mm	O500	A500
600 N/mm	O600	
750 N/mm		A750
900 N/mm	O900	A900

Table 2: Investigated panel structures

The labeling of the panels is derived from their associated design load, which is in this case the ultimate load. For example the panel label O500 is derived from an orthogrid panel with a compression design load of 500 N/mm, the anisogrid panels are labeled in the same manner. During the analytical sizing process of the anisogrid and orthogrid structures it has been determined that the anisogrid panels have on average approximately 10 % more weight than the orthogrid panels with the same design load.

3 NUMERICAL MODEL

The FEM simulations were performed with the commercial FE software ABAQUS. As a result of a mesh convergence study, the skin and blade stiffeners of the numerical model (Figure 2) consists of quadratic shell elements with eight nodes, reduced integration (S8R elements in ABAQUS) and an element length of 10 mm. The FE mesh of skin and the blade stiffeners for the orthogrid as well as the anisogrid panels is coincide, which means the element edges of skin and stiffeners correspond.

Figure 2: Finite Element Model of the anisogrid panel (left) and orthogrid panel (right)

For determining the load-displacement curves, geometrically nonlinear simulations with no imperfection are performed using the displacement controlled Newton-Raphson method with automatic stabilization. A convergence study regarding the damping factor D was performed for several panels, $D = 1e^{-7}$ was chosen. The displacement controlled load is applied in the axial direction of the panels which is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Loading of the panel structures

The mechanical boundary conditions used in the finite element simulation reflect the boundary conditions used in the analytical pre-design process. The out-of-plane displacement (u_z) along all edges is fixed. In order to prevent twisting of the stiffeners along the edges, the out-of-plane rotation (r_z) for the stiffeners at all edges has been fixed as well. Rigid body motions are inhibited by fixing the in-plane displacements (u_x & u_y) at one node at the centre of the panel structures.

4 RESULTS OF THE NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

The load-displacement and stiffness-load curves of the geometrically nonlinear simulations for the anisogrid A900 and orthogrid O900 are shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5.

Figure 4: Load-Displacement curve (left) and Relative Stiffness-Load curve (right) for the panel A900

The first buckling (local skin buckling) occurs shortly after the limit load (LL) has been exceeded. This behavior matches quite well with the analytical design criteria of the panels, which was skin buckling at limit load. The stiffness until limit load is nearly constant for both panels; however, the first buckling is accompanied by a significant drop of the panel stiffness. The panel stiffness of the anisogrid reduces on average about 6 % between limit and ultimate load, the stiffness reduction for the orthogrid panel is in this range nearly four times higher, on average about 22 %. The collapse of both panels occurs well after ultimate load. The Collapse load (CL) of A900 is 23 % higher in comparison to O900, but it should also be mentioned that A900 has approximately 10 % more weight.

Figure 5: Load-Displacement curve (left) and Relative Stiffness-Load curve (right) for the Panel O900

For the investigated panels, the ratio of collapse load to limit load was investigated. The associated results are listed in the Table 3-Table 4. It could be seen that the collapse load of the anisogrid panels is on average 2 times the limit load, for the orthogrid panels in contrast the collapse load is on average 1.75 times the limit load (Figure 6 - left).

This behavior results from a greater reduction of the orthogrid panel stiffness in comparison to the anisogrid panel stiffness which occurs between limit and ultimate load (Figure 6 - right). The results showed that the overall stiffness reduction between limit load and ultimate load for the anisogrid is on average 5%, the stiffness for the orthogrid reduces on average about 25 % between limit load and ultimate load (compare Figure 4-Figure 6).

Orthogrid	Stiffness Ratio UL / LL	Ratio CL / LL
O250	0.669	1.684
O500	0.731	1.763
O600	0.795	1.894
O900	0.784	1.670
Median	0.744	1.752

Table 3: Ratio of Stiffness at Ultimate Load / Stiffness at Limit Load and Ratio of Collapse Load / Limit Load for the flat orthogrid panels

Anisogrid	Stiffness Ratio UL / LL	Ratio CL / LL
A200	0.988	1.963
A250	0.976	2.171
A400	0.933	2.298
A500	0.997	2.132
A750	0.897	1.901
A900	0.942	1.984
Median	0.955	2.074

Table 4: Ratio of Stiffness at Ultimate Load / Stiffness at Limit Load and Ratio of Collapse Load / Limit Load for the flat anisogrid panels

Figure 6: Ratio of collapse load to ultimate load (left) and ratio of stiffness at ultimate load to limit load for the flat panels

A reason for this behavior can be seen in the post-buckling after initial first buckling (skin bay buckling). The local skin buckling pattern of the orthogrid switches (local skin buckles merge, buckles change position, buckle amplitude increases or switch in the opposite direction) in the area between local and ultimate load multiple times (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Buckling pattern of the orthogrid between limit and ultimate load

Every change in the buckling pattern (Figure 7 - top) of the orthogrid panel is accompanied by a significant reduction of the panel stiffness. In Figure 7 (bottom) a sectional view of the orthogrid panel is illustrated. The reduction of the panel stiffness is mainly caused by a reduction of the load carrying area of the skin fields which leads to an increasing loading of the blade stiffeners. The panel stiffness is nearly constant before any buckles appear (load condition 1). At load condition 2 several buckles appeared in the external skin fields (which cause a reduction of the load carrying skin field area); this leads to the first major reduction of the panel stiffness. The buckles in the external skin field's switch in the opposite direction at load condition 3, additional buckles appear in the center of the panel. The number of skin bay buckles increases even further at load condition 4. It can also be seen that the amplitude of the buckles increases at each load condition. This behavior and the increasing number of skin field buckles lead to an additional reduction of the load carrying skin field area. The load carrying capability of skin fields decreases even further when multiple small buckles merge into on big single buckles at load condition 5. The skin fields of the panel center have nearly no load carrying capability at load condition 5 therefore the surrounding stiffeners are burdened with an increased loading. This leads, shortly after ultimate load, to local stiffener buckling which results in global panel buckling and finally collapse of the panel structure. Figure 8 shows the panel stiffness and the associated sectional view of the anisogrid panel.

Figure 8: Buckling pattern of the anisogrid between limit and ultimate load

It can be seen that similar to the orthogrid panel, the panel stiffness of the anisogrid reduces shortly after limit load at load condition 2. Between load conditions 2-5 only the amplitude of the buckles increases, which leads to a relatively small reduction of the panel stiffness.

In contrast to the orthogrid panel, the anisogrid panel does not change the local skin buckling pattern. In consequence the stiffness reduction stays nearly linear until ultimate load.

The anisogrid panel shows in comparison to the orthogrid panel a benevolent post-buckling behavior.

5 STRUCTURAL ROBUSTNESS

Structural robustness is according to Starossek (2006) defined as the “insensitivity of a structure to local failure” [3]. In context with the investigated panels this means that a panel with a high structural robustness has no sharp collapse after local failure (local buckling in this case) but a progressive collapse.

Taguchi (2000) stated that “robustness is the state where the technology, product, or process performance is minimally sensitive to factors causing variability (either in the manufacturing or user’s environment) and aging at the lowest unit manufacturing cost” [4]. In the context with composite structures, factors which cause variability are inherent variation in material properties, ply orientation and ply thickness. Geometric imperfections, the deviation of the real structural shape from the theoretically perfect shape, cause variability as well as boundary conditions induced imperfect loading distributions into the structure.

In order to be structural robust a structure should have redundant components. Fu and Frangopol (1990) proposed the “redundancy index” based on the probability of failure of damaged and undamaged structures [5].

In context with the investigated panel’s redundant components are for example the load carrying skin and the load carrying stiffeners under axial compression. If the skin fields buckle (structure is “damaged”), their load carrying capability reduces significantly and the stiffeners are redundant components to guarantee that no sharp collapse occurs.

The buckling of the investigated structures is accompanied by a remarkable reduction of the panel stiffness which will inevitably lead to failure mechanism like ply failure and skin-stiffener debonding. Therefore a structural robustness measure should consider stiffness reduction and damage evolution.

A robustness measure which is damage and stiffness-based was proposed by Starossek and Haberland (2011) [6]. Their damage-based measure of robustness is derived from the ratio of “maximum total damage” and “acceptable total damage”. But a problem with this approach is that there is no definitive definition of an “acceptable damage” for buckling of skin-stiffener debonding of integral stiffened composite panels. The stiffness-based measure of robustness is derived from the ratio of “structural stiffness after removing a failed structural element” and “stiffness of the undamaged structure”. This measure is suitable when each structural element fails independently, and it is possible to access their stiffness individually. This approach is not appropriate for thin-walled composite structures in post-buckling because structural elements (skin and stiffener) are bonded and could fail simultaneously. The “Robust Index” according to Lee et al. (2010) is based on two parameters, the „influence and “sensitivity” [7]. This approach considers inherent variations and allows comparison of design concepts but an insensitivity to local failure (local buckling) is not measured. A distinct classification of a robust or not robust design is not possible with this robustness measure.

Da Cunha (2014) proposed a structural robustness measure which uses the energy until limit, ultimate and collapse load by calculating the area under the load-displacement curve [8]. Using this approach the reduction of stiffness due to buckling can be considered appropriately. It is also possible to take material failure or debonding into account because the strain energy of the entire system is included. This method can be easily applied to the calculated load-displacement curve of the anisogrid and orthogrid panels (numerical integration of the load-displacement curve until LL, UL and CL with for example the trapezoidal rule), the different energy components are illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Energy components for A900 – energy until limit load (left) – energy until ultimate load (middle) – energy until collapse load (right)

According to Da Cunha the limit load can be identified by a small reduction of the relative stiffness of the panels. The ultimate load within this paper is defined as 1.5 times the limit load. The collapse load is the maximum load in the load-displacement curve. The energy until the characteristic points LL, UL and CL are given in Table 5-Table 6 for the orthogrid panels as well as the anisogrid panels. The different energy measures are used to create an energy-based robustness index [8], which is defined as shown in equation (1):

$$R_{ELUL} = 1 - E_{UL}/E_{CL}, 0 < R_{ELUL} < 1 \quad (1)$$

According to [8] an index equal to 0 indicates “non-robustness”. A theoretical “perfect robustness” would be achieved if it equals unity. In Table 5 - Table 6 are the results for the investigated panels (compare Figure 10).

Orthogrid	Energy until LL [Nmm]	Energy until UL [Nmm]	Energy until CL [Nmm]	$R_{EL,UL}$
O250	38.9	95.5	160.8	0.40
O500	113.6	281.8	480.7	0.41
O600	148.2	364.3	576.8	0.36
O900	282.1	686.9	981.0	0.29
Median				0.37

Table 5: Robustness assessment of the orthogrid panels

Anisogrid	Energy until LL [Nmm]	Energy until UL [Nmm]	Energy until CL [Nmm]	$R_{EL,UL}$
A200	27.1	63.9	160.0	0.60
A250	37.0	86.9	226.9	0.61
A400	69.6	166.3	406.1	0.59
A500	104.5	245.6	548.0	0.55
A750	215.9	499.0	977.4	0.48
A900	275.3	630.6	1418.7	0.55
Median				0.56

Table 6: Robustness assessment of the anisogrid panels

Figure 10: Robustness Index for the flat panels

The results for the panels show that the anisogrid panels have on average a $R_{EL,UL} = 0.56$ and the orthogrid panels in comparison only have $R_{EL,UL} = 0.37$.

This means that the anisogrid panels have on average a 51 % higher structural robustness than the orthogrid panels. According to equation (1) a panel has a high structural robustness whose energy until collapse is much bigger than the energy until ultimate load, resulting in a high energy reserve. The results of chapter 4 show the post-buckling behavior of the anisogrid panel is in contrast to orthogrid panel benevolent. In consequence the collapse load of the anisogrid panels is on average about 18 % higher than the collapse load of the orthogrid panels (compare Table 3 and Table 4). This means the associated area under the load-shortening curve (energy) is correspondingly higher hence the higher structural robustness.

6 CONCLUSION

The structural robustness, a measure for the sensitivity of a structure to local failure, was investigated for anisogrid and orthogrid structures. The design parameters for the examined panels were defined in a way that the only difference between the two panels is the stiffener alignment. Ten different panels, four orthogrid panels and six anisogrid panels, were analytically pre-designed for this investigation. In order to analyze the structural robustness of the panels, geometrically non-linear FEM simulation of the post-buckling behavior were performed and the strain energy under the load-shortening curve at specific points (energy until limit, ultimate and collapse load) has been calculated. The results showed that the investigated anisogrid panels in contrast to the orthogrid panels have a very benevolent post-buckling behavior between limit load and ultimate load leading to an on average 18 % higher collapse load and correspondingly higher strain energy. According to the used robustness index [8], a structure has a high structural robustness whose energy until collapse is much higher than the energy until ultimate load. It was determined that this is the case for the anisogrid panels, which results in an on average 51% higher structural robustness in comparison to the orthogrid panels.

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